

A STUDY ON POSITIVE CLASSROOM MILIEU AND RATIONAL BELIEVES AMONG IX STANDARD STUDENTS

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Abstract

This study examined the Positive Classroom Milieu and Rational Believes among IX Standard Student. This study adopted normative survey method of research participants were 300 IX standard Students randomly selected from various schools. The Research Instruments used for data collection was Positive Classroom Milieu and Rational Believes was prepared and standardized by Investigator tested at 0.05 and 0.01 level of significance. The level of positive classroom milieu and Rational believes among IX standard students are moderate in nature. The result revealed that there is significant relationship between Positive Classroom milieu and Rational believes among IX standard students.

Keywords: Positive classroom milieu, rational believes, school students, behaviour, modification etc...

INTRODUCTION

Education in the broadest general sense is the through which the aims and habits of a group of people lives in from one generation to the next. Education is the deliberation and systematic influence exerted by the mature person upon the immature through instruction, discipline and harmonious development of physical, intellectual, aesthetic, social and spiritual powers of human being according to the individual with his creator as the final end. A comprehensive set of strategies meant to redesign environments in such a way that problem behaviours are prevented or inconsequential, and to teach students new skills, making problem behaviours unnecessary. Process intended to shift focus from negative responses, punishment, and responsive methods of address appropriate behaviours. It also includes the teaching of appropriate expected behaviours, restructuring of environments and preventing the occurrence of problem behaviours through behavioural intervention.

Classroom environment is closely linked to issues of motivation, discipline and respect. Methodologies remain a matter of passionate debate among teacher. The approaches vary depending on the beliefs a teacher holds regarding educational psychology. A large part of traditional classroom environment involves behaviour modification, although many teachers use behavioural approaches alone as overly simplistic. Many teachers establish rules and procedures at the beginning of the school year.

REVIEW OF THE RELATED LITERATURE

Studies related to Positive Classroom Milieu

Giallo (2013) conducted on “classroom Behaviour Problems: The relationship between preparedness significantly associated with levels of teacher self-efficiency in behaviour management. Therefore, with improved training and support, teachers will be in a position to deal with classroom misbehaviour confidently and effectively, lowering the risk of stress and burnout, as classroom Experiences, and self-efficacy in Graduate and student Teachers”. This study has concluded on preparedness and classroom experiences as factors that are well as provide an optimum learning environment for all students in the classroom.

M. Vellaisamy (2003) investigated on “A study of Environmental Achievement in IX standard student through environmental awareness”. The study conclusion is that students are not performing their role properly and systematically at high level in strengthening environmental education. Therefore, students’ involvement is needed in optimum level for above mentioned roles in strengthening the environmental awareness. Also, the student’s roles are not satisfied to protect the national resources.

Studies related to Rational Believes

Barry Lam (2011) investigated on “On the Rationality of Belief-Invariance in Light of peer Disagreement”. This study summarized on if you are currently a reliable epistemic agent in some domain, you would not want to adopt a rule of belief-revision in that domain that rendered you less reliable. However, you probably would want to adopt a rule that rendered you more reliable in that domain. In the epistemology of disagreement, there are two main competing rules offered for belief-revision in the face of peer disagreement: maintaining your existing opinion or meeting halfway. This article investigates the comparative reliability of these two rules using two measures of reliability for degrees of belief, calibration and Brier scoring. Using one measure of reliability, it can be shown that necessarily, meeting halfway is the more reliable rule. Using another measure of reliability, it can be shown that generally, belief-invariance is the more reliable rule. This article argues from these formal result belief-invariance in light of peer disagreement is sometimes rationally permissible and that, even when it is not, being required to revise your opinions in light of peer disagreement does not lead any kind of problematic scepticism.

Statement of the Study

The statement of the problem entitled “**A Study on Positive Classroom Milieu and Rational Believes among IX Standard Students.**”

Need and Significance of the Study

The school environment has a significant influence on the personality and development of students, as the school plays an important role the influence of positive classroom and positive thinking has been considered. Positive classroom helps to develop a child in all possible ways. Such as self-confidence, peer relationships, communication, improve skills. It helps the

children to attain various cognitive abilities and emotional connections. This study helps to develop a classroom environment which in turn may develop the rational thinking.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To find out the level of Positive classroom milieu of IX standard students.
2. To find out the level of rational believes of IX standard students.
3. To find out is there any difference in positive classroom milieu of IX standard students based on,
 - ✓ Gender
 - ✓ Types of management
 - ✓ Student Locality
 - ✓ Medium of Instruction
 - ✓ Locality of school
 - ✓ Father Educational status
 - ✓ Mother Educational status
 - ✓ Father occupational level
 - ✓ Mother occupational level
 - ✓ Parent's annual income
4. To find out is there any difference in rational believes of IX standard students based on,
 - ✓ Gender
 - ✓ Types of management
 - ✓ Student Locality
 - ✓ Medium of Instruction
 - ✓ Locality of school
 - ✓ Father Educational status
 - ✓ Mother Educational status
 - ✓ Father occupational level
 - ✓ Mother occupational level
 - ✓ Parent's annual income
5. To find out the relationship between positive classroom milieu and relational believes among IX standard students.

Hypothesis of the Study

1. The level of positive classroom milieu of IX standard students is moderate.
2. The level of rational believes of IX standard students is moderate.
3. Boys and Girls do not differ significant in them
 - a) Positive classroom milieu
 - b) Rational believes
4. Student's studying in different management of schools differ do not significantly in them
 - a) Positive classroom milieu
 - b) Rational believes
5. Student's belonging to rural and urban area do not differ significantly in them
6. Student's studying in differ medium of instruction do not differ significantly in them
 - a) Positive classroom milieu
 - b) Rational believes
7. Student's school studying in rural and urban schools do not differ significantly in them
 - a) Positive classroom milieu
 - b) Rational believes
8. Student's who's with different father's educational level differ significantly in their
 - a) Positive classroom milieu
 - b) Rational believes
9. Student's who's with different mother's educational level differ significantly in their
 - a) Positive classroom milieu
 - b) Rational Believes
10. Student's belonging to different occupational level of the fathers different significantly in them
 - a) Positive classroom milieu
 - b) Rational believes
11. Student's belonging to different occupational level of the mothers different significantly in them
 - a) Positive classroom milieu
 - b) Rational believes

12. Student's belonging to different annual income of the parents differ significantly in them
- a) Positive classroom milieu
 - b) Relational believes
13. There is no significant difference between positive classrooms Milieu and rational believes among IX standard students.

METHOD OF THE STUDY

In the present study random sampling method is employed. This method is used to describe and interpret, what exist at present. It is concerned with the condition of relationships that exist; practices that prevail, beliefs, point of view are attitude that are held, process that are on-going and effects that are being felt. Data are gathered, tabulated, classified, interpreted, compared, evaluated and then generalizations are made.

Tools used for the Study

The tool is an instrument, which is used to collect data from the sample. In the present study, the tool namely positive classroom milieu and rational believes among IX standard students was developed by the Investigator and her supervisor. This can be used to measure the positive classroom milieu and rational believes among IX standard students.

1. Personal Data sheet developed by the investigator and the supervisor.
2. Positive Classroom milieu among IX standard students developed by the investigator and the supervisor.
3. Rational believes among IX standard students developed by the investigator and the supervisor.

Sampling and Sampling Technique

The size of the sample is 300 were selected from various institutions at cluster sampling technique. The distribution of the sample is shown in the below table:

Table 1: Distribution of the Sample

Variables	Category	N	Percentage
Gender	Male	124	41.3
	Female	176	58.7
Medium of Instruction	Tamil	127	42.3
	English	173	57.7
Student Locality	Urban	122	40.7
	Rural	178	59.3
Type of School	Government	100	33.3
	Govt. Aided	106	33.3
	Private	94	31.3
School Locality	Urban	50	16.7
	Rural	250	83.3
Fathers Qualification	Uneducated	37	12.3
	1-10	114	38
	10-12	78	26
	UG	47	15
	PG	24	8
Mother Qualification	Uneducated	52	17.3
	1-10	144	48
	10-12	73	24.3
	UG	25	8.3
	PG	6	2
Father Occupation	Self employed	164	54.7
	Government	54	18
	Private	82	27.3
Mother Occupation	Self-Employment	274	91.3
	Government	19	6.3
	Private	7	2.3
Family Income	20000	133	44.3
	20000-40000	92	30.7
	Above 40000	75	25

Figure 1: Distribution of the Sample

Statistical Techniques Used for Data Analysis

In the present study following statistical techniques were used and done by SPSS Package.

1. Descriptive Analysis (Mean, Standard Deviation)
2. Different Analysis (t-values, F-ratios)
3. Correlative Analysis

Table 2: The Level of Positive Classroom Milieu among IX Standard Students

Variable	Level	N	Percentage
Positive Classroom Milieu	Low	76	25.33%
	Moderate	183	61%
	High	41	13.67%

Table: 2 shows that 25.33%, 61%, 13.67% of the samples have Low, Moderate, and High levels of positive classroom milieu among IX standard students. Based on the results, it can be concluded that the level of positive classroom milieu among IX standard students of the majority of IX standard students are moderate (61%) in nature.

Figure 2: The level of positive classroom milieu among IX standard students

Table 3: The Level of Rational Believes Among IX Standard Students

Variable	Level	N	Percentage
Rational Believes	Low	127	42.33%
	Moderate	140	46.67%
	High	33	11%

Table: 3 shows that 42.33%, 46.67%, 11% of the samples have Low, Moderate, and High levels of rational believes among IX standard students. Based on the results, it can be concluded that the level of rational believes among IX standard students of the majority of IX standard students are moderate (46.67%) in nature.

Figure 3: Figure showing the level of rational Believes among IX standard students

Table 4: Correlation between Positive Classroom and Rational Believes among Total Sample of IX Standard Students

Variables	N	'r' value	Level of significance
Positive classroom Milieu	300	0.342	p>0.01
Rational Believes	300		

The table: 4 shows that the significance relationship between Positive classroom Milieu and Rational Believes of IX Standard Students. The calculated p-value is >0.01 levels and it is statistically significant at 0.01 levels. Therefore, the null hypothesis i.e., “there is no relationship between Positive classroom Milieu and Rational Believes of IX standard students” is rejected. It is inferred that there is a positive correlation between positive classroom Milieu and Rational Believes of IX standard students.

Delimitation of the study

1. The present study has been restricted to IX standard students.
2. Only students studying in selected schools in Thanjavur city alone have been considered for the study.
3. Three types of school's (Government, Government aided, and private schools) has been included in this study. 300 students alone have been taken for the present study.

Major Findings

1. The level of positive classroom milieu among IX standard students is moderate Level.
2. The level of Rational believes among IX standard students is moderate Level.
3. Boys and Girls do not differ significantly with respect to Positive classroom milieu.
4. Boys and Girls do not differ significantly with respect to Rational Believes.
5. Students studying in Tamil and English medium differ significantly with respect to Positive classroom milieu.
6. Students studying in Tamil and English medium differ significantly with respect to Rational Believes.
7. Students belonging to Rural and Urban area differ significantly with respect to Positive classroom milieu.
8. Students belonging to Rural and Urban area do not differ significantly with respect to Rational Believes.
9. Students studying in different Management of school differ significantly with respect to Positive classroom milieu.
10. Students studying in different Management of school differ significantly with respect to Rational Believes.

11. Students studying in Rural and Urban school differ significantly with respect to Positive classroom milieu.
12. Students studying in Rural and Urban school differ significantly with respect to Rational Believes.
13. Student whose father education level differs significantly with respect to Positive classroom milieu.
14. Student whose father education level differ significantly with respect to Rational Believes.
15. Student whose Mother education level differ significantly with respect to Positive classroom milieu.
16. Student whose Mother education level differ significantly with respect to Rational Believe.
17. Students belonging to different occupational level of the Father differ significantly with respect to Positive classroom milieu.
18. Students belonging to different occupational level of the Father differ significantly with respect to Rational Believes.
19. Students belonging to different occupational level of the mother do not differ significantly with respect to positive classroom milieu.
20. Students belonging to different occupational level of the Mother do not differ significantly with respect to Rational Believes.
21. Students belonging to different Family income of the parents differ significantly with respect to Positive classroom milieu.
22. Students belonging to different Family income of the parents differ significantly with respect to Rational Believes.

DISCUSSIONS

1. Based on the finding of result there is no significant difference in Positive classroom milieu with respect to gender. Male students have high positive classroom milieu than the female students. Because of the more encourage, daring and interactive than in classrooms. It is also understood that there is no significant difference in Rational believes with respect to gender. Male students have high Rational believes than the female students. Because usually boys take their own decisions withoutany hesitations. They do not depend on others. Based on the finding of result there is significant difference in Positive classroom milieu with respect to medium of instruction. Tamil medium students have high positive classroom milieu than the English medium students. Since they learn their subjects in mother tongue. It is also understood that there is significant difference in Rational believes with respect to medium of instruction. Tamil medium students have high Rational believes than the English medium students. Since their Tamil medium students develop more skills overcome distraction and obstacles in making appropriate correct decisions. Based on the

findings of results there is significant difference in Positive classroom milieu with respect to Student Locality. Rural students have high Positive classroom milieu than the urban students. Because they are very enthusiastic and interest in going to schools. It is also understood that there is no significant difference in Rational believes with respect to student locality. Rural students have high Rational believes than the urban students. Because on decision making since they are guided by the parents, Grandparents and relatives as they mostly grow in joint families.

2. Based on findings of result there is significant difference in Positive classroom milieu with respect to Type of management. Government school students have high positive classroom milieu than the private school students. Because they have more opportunities to develop their skills using their own creativity. It is also understood that there is significant difference in Rational Believes with respect to Type of Management. Government aided school students have high Rational believes than the private school students. Because they teachers are qualified and produced the students who can decided they and their own. Based on the findings of result there is significant difference in positive classroom milieu with respect to school locality. Rural area school students have high positive classroom milieu than the urban area school students. Because they are very enthusiastic and interested in going to schools. It is also understood that there is significant difference in Rational believes with respect to school Locality. Rural area school students have high Rational believes than the urban area school students. Because on decision making since they are guided by the parents, Grandparents and relatives as they mostly grow in joint families.
3. Based on the findings of results there is significant difference in positive classroom milieu with respect to father educational level. The children of uneducated fathers have high positive classroom milieu than the children of UG fathers. It is also understood that there is significant difference in Rational believes with respect to father educational level. The children of uneducated fathers have high Rational believes than the children of 12th level of fathers. Based on the findings of result there is significant difference in Positive classroom milieu with respect to mother educational level. The children of 10th standard Mothers have high positive classroom milieu than the children of UG Mothers. It is also understood that results there is significant difference in Rational believes with respect to mother educational level. The children of uneducated mothers have high Rational believes than the children of UG Mothers.
4. Based on the findings of results there is significant difference in positive classroom milieu with respect to father occupational level. The children of self-employed occupation of fathers have high positive classroom milieu than the children of private occupation of fathers. It is also understood that there is significant difference in rational believes with respect to father occupation level. The children of self-employed occupation of fathers have high Rational believes than the children of private occupation of fathers. Based on the findings of results there is significant difference in Positive classroom milieu with respect to Family income. Children from the families which have low income have more positive classroom milieu than the high income level. It is also understood that there is significant

difference in rational believes with respect to family income. Children from the families which have low income have more positive classroom milieu than the high income level.

Educational Implications of the Present Study

On the basis of the finding of the study the following implications has been made by the investigator.

1. To create a positive classroom environment we should be tried to instill a sense of community among students throw co-operative learning activities. Classroom routines should be altered frequently.
2. To foster a development the Higher-order thinking skills planned assignments must be given. Every student must be treated with equal care and respect. The classroom must be made by friendlier, Understanding, Respectively, Patient, Fair and helping.
3. To improve Rational thinking practices such as decision analysis, problem analysis situation appraisal techniques can be used. Rational thinking also may also be developed by making thinking as a visible process. Rational thinking also develops by working and thinking with others. So team assignments, group works can be given. Rational process also develops by co-operative learning techniques. Steps which can be to improve rational thinking are encouragement, support, guiding, providing of frame work, strategies to help them to handle real life issues and problems.

CONCLUSION

The school plays an important role in developing the personality of the students. The influence of positive classroom and positive thinking helps to develop a child in all possible ways. It helps the children to attain various cognitive abilities and develop ability. This study helps to develop a classroom environment which is turn may develop the rational thinking of the children.

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